

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

Actor-specific leverage points for transformative change

Deliverable 5.3

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

International supply chains that comprise production, processing, trading, manufacturing, and retail of forest and agricultural commodities and derived products connect supply- and demand-side countries and regions around the globe. These “telecoupled” systems, where causes and effects along supply chains transcend national borders, constitute a challenging context for their transnational regulation and governance. Focusing on the new European Union Regulation on Deforestation-free products (EUDR) as a transnational environmental public policy regulating supply chains, but looking also beyond it towards a broader suite of policies, this report pursues three objectives: i) To synthesize key insights from CLEVER Deliverables 4.3, 5.1 and 5.2, complemented by other lines of evidence, ii) to gauge the potential environmental and socio-economic effects and effectiveness of the EUDR, and iii) to summarize qualitative evidence on actor-specific leverage points for biodiversity positive transformative change along international non-food biomass supply chains.

For the first two objectives, we develop a Theory of Change (ToC) for the EUDR, outlining the regulation's intended main overarching impact (i.e., contributing to a reduction in global forest loss) and how it can be presumed to come to being. This includes making assumptions underlying the ToC explicit, framed as conditions (factors that threaten to undermine the designed main EUDR effect) and boosters (factors that could enhance the main EUDR effect beyond the minimum intended). Insights from CLEVER Deliverables 4.3, 5.1 and 5.2 synthesized along the EUDR's ToC suggest several opportunities and pitfalls for the EUDR's effectiveness. Regarding forward-looking opportunities, the scope of the EUDR could be expanded (e.g., in terms of commodities, biomes) in future revisions of the regulation, the EUDR could exhibit more coherence with already existing national and transnational regulatory instruments in supply-side countries, and a ‘Brussels effect’ could lead to the EUDR standards being adopted or followed by governments and/or companies outside of the EU. Such developments would positively influence the effectiveness of the EUDR. Pitfalls include possible monitoring and enforcement shortcoming in the EU, market segregation taking place for most commodities due to the EU's small global market shares, and the regulation resulting in marginalization and exclusion of smallholders from the EU market due to their limited capacity to adhere to the EUDR's requirements. The analysis shows how “clean” EU-bound supply chains of forest-risk commodities (FRC) – if these were to be achieved – do not necessarily translate into a reduction in global deforestation and forest degradation levels.

Furthermore, interviews with actors involved in or knowledgeable about Cameroon-EU and Gabon-EU timber supply chains, and EU-Brazil soy, wood pulp and timber supply chains (e.g., public and private actors, non-governmental organizations) indicate notable reservations in their belief about the EUDR's future effectiveness at the global level. According to interviewees, important

reasons for possible EUDR ineffectiveness include market spillover and segregation effects, and the small initial EU share of the global market of many commodities that reduces policy leverage. At the same time, to the extent these issues can be addressed or contained, they could spell positive for EUDR effectiveness. In addition, interviewees highlighted that the EUDR's future effectiveness at the global level depends on regulatory alignment with and political support by other countries, meaning that only if other countries (e.g., China) adopt similar regulations can the EUDR be expected to be effective vis-à-vis its overarching environmental goals. Also, as interviewees argued, if producing countries do not politically endorse and support the EUDR and its implementation – due to a prevalent feeling among them that it was unilaterally designed and imposed by the EU – the EUDR will become ineffective.

While the EUDR's effectiveness could be enhanced through various leverage points along its ToC, it is important to explicitly consider leverage points (i.e., places within a complex system where a small shift in one thing can produce big changes in everything) also in a wider policy context, for different reasons. For example, a single instrument like the EUDR cannot be expected to solemnly address all issues facing the legality and sustainability of forest and agricultural commodity supply chains. Against this context, we gathered interviewees' views on what or where they would see the most important leverage points for conserving biodiversity and reducing deforestation and forest degradation. Some of the most frequently raised leverage points were: ensure monitoring and enforcement for legal compliance; positive economic and market incentives; strengthen and support local capacities; collaboration and partnerships, and political will; clarify land tenure and policy, and address land grabbing and speculation; Brussels effect (vis-à-vis the EUDR); and payments for ecosystem services. In terms of the mechanism of all leverage points, interviewees mostly raised leverage points that act as enabling factors, facilitating various conditions that can help ensure good governance and legality and/or sustainability of production and consumption. Beyond that, interviewees indicated a preference for “positive” (e.g., incentives) over “negative” (e.g., disincentives) signals as leverage points. In terms of leverage point type, most leverage points can be seen as area-based (over supply chain-based, for instance), indicating a lower recognition or preference for transnational governance measures.

When interpreting the role of actors in relation to the different leverage points, two overarching observations can be made. First, most leverage points were indicated for the supply side. This speaks about the importance of supply side measures and the role supply side actors have in creating transformative change. It also underscores the crucial aspect of international collaboration, so that supply- and demand-side actors can work together to address issues and challenges. This is all the more important, as trade-based demand-side measures like the EUDR provide limited leverage over biodiversity positive transformative change along international non-food biomass supply chains. Second, public

actors arguably have a sole or key role in many of the most-mentioned leverage points, such as ensuring monitoring and enforcement, political will, clarifying land tenure and land policy, and revising regulatory frameworks. As such, it can be essential to seek ways to exploit these leverage points, having a leading role by public actors whilst ensuring the inclusion of complementary actors in these processes.

1 INTRODUCTION

The ongoing forest loss globally, and particularly in the tropics and subtropics, is largely attributable to non-sustainable and/or illegal land-use change, agriculture and forestry practices (Pendriil et al., 2022; Vancutsem et al., 2021), threatening biodiversity, livelihoods, and efforts to combat climate change (Buckley & Liesch, 2023; CPF, 2018). The non-sustainable and illegal production of so-called forest risk commodities (FRCs), such as soy, timber, and beef, is linked to global environmental risks such as deforestation and forest degradation. FRC are also often linked to international trade: in the period 2010–2014, 29–39% of tropical deforestation-related emissions were driven by international trade (Pendriil et al., 2019). The ensuing supply chains – comprising production, processing, trading, manufacturing, and retail of forest and agricultural commodities and derived products – connect supply and demand side countries and regions around the globe. These “telecoupled” systems, where causes and effects along supply chains transcend national borders, constitute a challenging context for their transnational regulation and governance (Meyfroidt et al., 2013).

Indeed, various policies and governance mechanisms, such as domestic policies and regulations (e.g., the national forestry laws of tropical and non-tropical countries), public transnational regulations (e.g., timber legality laws and laws on deforestation-free commodities in the EU, the UK, the US, Australia), and private translational initiatives (e.g., voluntary corporate zero-deforestation commitments; third party sustainability and legality certification schemes) attempt to regulate the legality and/or sustainability of international FRC supply chains or parts thereof (Sotirov et al., 2020; Berning et al., 2023). However, measured against the persisting rate of forest loss and the established role that agricultural and forest products continue to play in it, the effectiveness of these various instruments, despite some positive developments, has arguably so far remained limited (Lambin et al., 2018; Sotirov et al. 2020).

In this context, our analytical focus in this Deliverable will be on the European Union (EU) Regulation on Deforestation-free Products (EUDR) that was recently adopted to help address some of the still persisting deforestation and forest degradation issues. The EUDR has garnered sustained hopes for eliminating deforestation and forest degradation linked to agricultural and forestry products attributable to the EU market's consumption, and beyond (European Union, 2023). The EUDR, whose implementation phase has been delayed by one year to 30 December 2025, mandates businesses that place for the first time or make available various FRCs or derived products on the EU market (covering import, selling, and export) to ensure that they are legally produced and free of deforestation and forest degradation. The EUDR holds obligations targeted to businesses who use the EU marketplace to submit a due diligence statement confirming compliance with the EUDR's legality and deforestation-free standards. Whilst the regulation does not place legal obligations on business actors outside the EU, producers and suppliers in non-EU countries will need to provide certain

information (e.g., geolocations of the plots where products were grown/harvested) to downstream actors for products destined for the EU market, so that all businesses placing for the first time or making available products on the EU market can fulfil their obligations. This also covers commodities and products originating from within the EU that may be consumed in the EU market or exported from it. The EUDR is thus set to function as a conditioned quantitative restriction on trade. (Berning & Sotirov, 2023, 2024; Oliveira et al., 2024; Sotirov et al., 2022)

Various aspects of the EUDR and its role in regulating international supply chains have hitherto also been scrutinized in CLEVER Work Package 4 and 5 Deliverables. Deliverable 4.3 analyzed the policy (in)coherences in the regulatory design between the EUDR and three national public policies (i.e., the national public forest laws of Brazil, Cameroon and Gabon) and three hybrid public-private governance mechanisms (i.e., Brazilian Amazon Soy Moratorium, EU-Cameroon Voluntary Partnership Agreement (VPA), and Gabon Mandatory FSC Certification) from non-EU producer countries (i.e., Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon). Deliverable 5.1 examined how business actors (as key regulated actor under the EUDR) in five focal supply chains (Brazil-EU soy, timber, and wood pulp, and Cameroon-EU and Gabon-EU timber) would self-statedly respond to the EUDR. Deliverable 5.2 explored indirect effects and spillover mechanisms that may either hinder or support the main functionality of the EUDR.

Together, these three Deliverables highlight implications for the potential effects and effectiveness of the EUDR. Other scientific literature has also begun inspecting these issues in relation to the EUDR but often informed by experience with earlier instruments and/or with reference to national policy, legal, and socio-economic frameworks in the producer countries (Azevedo-Ramos & Murakami Lima, 2024; Köthke et al., 2023; Muradian et al., 2025; Zhong et al., 2024; Zhunusova et al., 2022). For example, Muradian et al. (2025) discuss the risks and limitations of the EUDR derived from an ex-ante normative assessment of the robustness of its theory of change (ToC), highlighting several drawbacks and risks associated with the regulation's constitutive features: to be exclusively demand-oriented and focused on the supply chain as the unit of intervention, and to hold a high degree of unilateralism.

However, despite the fact that the EUDR is primarily a regulatory tool working with economic disincentives, existing research has paid insufficient attention to economic and policy considerations in the EUDR, which we will address here. Also, unlike earlier research that is based on secondary data and lessons drawing from past experiences, our study is, additionally, methodologically and empirically grounded by primary data. As such, we aim to develop a better understanding of the EUDR's change logic (i.e., its ToC) based on stakeholder perceptions of EUDR effectiveness and leverage points (beyond the EUDR) along supply chains. Improving this knowledge could provide more objective insights and nuanced expectations about how impactful the EUDR would likely be in

addressing global forest loss issues, as well as informing discussions about the need for complementary policy measures. The insights could also inform the EUDR's general periodic review, and the design of other similar policies and governance mechanisms being implemented or designed or under discussion in other consumer regions (e.g., the UK, the US). Moreover, our insights also inform impact evaluations (e.g., Deliverable 3.3), simulation/modeling and foresight studies (e.g., Deliverables 7.3-4) to evaluate ex-ante or ex-post the EUDR's effects and effectiveness.

Thus, in this Deliverable we seek to answer the following key questions:

1. Based on the currently available knowledge, what are the EUDR's potential environmental and socio-economic effects, and likely overall effectiveness as a supply chain intervention?
2. What leverage points for transformative change exist along the inspected supply chains subject to the EUDR?

We aim to answer these questions based on a synthesis of key research results from CLEVER work packages 4 (analysis of the design of the EUDR and other supply chain interventions) and 5 (analysis of policy implementation with focus on the EUDR). In addition, the synthesis is complemented by semi-structured key informant interviews (e.g., with public and private actors), and empirically informed literature on the EUDR and other supply chain-focused policies and governance mechanisms, as later detailed in Section 3.

The report is structured as follows: Sections 2 and 3 outline the Deliverable's objectives and methodology, respectively. Section 4 details the EUDR's ToC. Building on this, Section 5 draws on stakeholder interviews to discuss the EUDR's potential effects and effectiveness and explore leverage points beyond the EUDR along supply chains. Finally, we conclude and synthesize in sections 6 and 7, respectively.

2 OBJECTIVES

This Deliverable has three objectives:

- (i) To synthesize key insights from CLEVER Deliverables 4.3, 5.1 and 5.2, complemented by other lines of evidence.
- (ii) To gauge the potential environmental and socio-economic effects and effectiveness of the EUDR.
- (iii) To summarize qualitative evidence on actor-specific leverage points for biodiversity positive transformative change along international non-food biomass supply chains.

3 CONCEPTUAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

Different qualitative approaches exist for studying, ex ante or ex post, the effects and effectiveness of policy and regulatory interventions. For example, Efroymsen et al. (2016) developed a causal analysis framework for analyzing effects and the probable causes (e.g., interventions) of the effects in the context of land use change. Especially applicable to ex-post analysis, the core of the framework is a so-called strength-of-evidence approach, which provides for drawing on multiple lines of evidence to determine the presence or absence of causal relationships between causes and effects. Causal analysis, which is a formal process that uses evidence to infer causal relations or to link effects and causes, allows producing probable rather than just plausible change models (Efroymsen et al., 2016).

Another, yet related approach of applying a logical framework to the causal chain of an intervention is the ToC, constituting “the description of a sequence of events that is expected to lead to a particular desired outcome” (Vogel, 2012, p. 9). Hence, it is an analytical tool to explore and map the designed and expected change logic of an intervention.

In the policy evaluation and impact assessment literature, a ToC causal chain usually separates different consecutive steps, commonly depicted in five levels: input, treatment, output, outcome, and impact (Weiss 2018). In the context of supply chain interventions, input refers to legal/formal provisions and resources (e.g. financial, informational) mobilized to implement a treatment (i.e., a purpose-driven intervention) that aims to eventually achieve change as designed in these regulatory standards. As such, treatment captures formal implementation and enforcement processes of the provisions from input. Output represents the completed treatment and describes behavioral changes of actors on the ground (e.g., regulatory targets, changed attitudes, signed contracts). Outcomes refer to immediate effects from the actors' behavioral changes at the system level (e.g., changed land uses, planted trees). Impact represents long-term, ultimate effects as defined by the intervention, taking place at the macro-level (e.g., increased ecosystem services, boosted landowner incomes). The difference between outcomes and impacts lies in that outcomes can be reliably and directly attributed to the intervention, while impacts are rather considered as going beyond the intervention “accounting ceiling” (e.g., because they are driven also by factors other than the targeted intervention) (Niel et al., 2020).

Importantly, a ToC approach highlights the need to make explicit the role of assumptions underlying a change logic. An assumption, in this context, can be broadly understood as “a proposition that is taken for granted, without reference to the facts” and it can range from “ideas about the context, ideas about the drivers of change, ideas about the cause-effect relationships between

interventions, outcomes and context, as well as individual and organisational values" (Vogel, 2012, p. 26). In fact, the central idea in ToC thinking is making critical assumptions explicit (Martius et al., 2018; Vogel, 2012), which can function as a check of how effective (supply chain) interventions were, are, could, would (analytical perspective), or should be (normative perspective).

We adopt the ToC as an analytical approach for the objectives of this Deliverable. On the one hand, aligned with the analytical focus of Work Package 4 and 5 Deliverables, we focus on the EUDR as a regulatory intervention that has not yet entered its implementation phase (albeit certain preparations and discussions about implementation have already started). Notably, the ToC analysis integrates both the intended causal pathways and effects on behalf of the implementers (here, the European Commission) and alternative, including possible contrarian effects which other analysts might point to: the ToC is a place where advocates and critics can come together. On the other hand, ToC provides for a flexible approach that is suited for an ex-ante analysis, which is required in the case of current early stage of the EUDR. At the same time, the strength-of-evidence approach and the ToC approach are highly complementary, both being focused on causal analysis.

We develop the EUDR ToC based on the analysis of the EUDR legal text itself and related state-of-the-art knowledge (e.g., scientific literature, CLEVER project outputs). In this way, we outline the key elements on the input-treatment-output-outcomes-impact model related to the assessment of the EUDR effectiveness. The ToC will present a presumed change logic of how the intervention is intended to function by design. Additionally, we identify critical assumptions underlying the change logic, framed as conditions and boosters. The conditions represent assumptions that – if not realized – threaten to undermine the designed main EUDR effect (i.e., contributing to a reduction in global deforestation). The boosters are not "needed" per se for achieving the main EUDR effect, but their presence could enhance it beyond the minimum intended. As such, the conditions and boosters serve as moderators to the main EUDR effect along the ToC causal chain and probe how relevant or probable the designed transitions along the ToC steps are and would/could/should be.

In reflecting on the EUDR ToC and the assumptions underlying it, we draw on different lines of evidence. This includes a synthesis of the key insights related to the EUDR from CLEVER Work Packages 4 and 5, mainly Deliverables 4.3 (Assessing horizontal and vertical policy and regulatory governance (in)coherence), 5.1 (Behavioral responses to value chain related policies and governance initiatives), and 5.2 (Qualitative assessment of leakage and other spillover potentials in selected value chains). Furthermore, we cite empirical literature on the EUDR and other, related policies and governance mechanisms (e.g., the EU Timber Regulation (EUTR)). We thus analyze leverage points related to the EUDR along its ToC. We define leverage points as "places within a complex system where a

small shift in one thing can produce big changes in everything" (Meadows, 1999, p. 1).

Complementing this, in section 5 we analyze actor perceptions of EUDR's effectiveness and leverage points (beyond the EUDR) based on semi-structured key informant interviews, with a focus on the Cameroon-EU and Gabon-EU timber supply chains, and EU-Brazil soy, wood pulp and timber supply chains (see Supplementary Material for the interview guide). The interviewed actors were public actors, international organizations, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), research/training institutions, think tanks, consultants, certification, finance, businesses, and business associations/federations involved in or knowledgeable about the five focal value chains. The methodological details behind the interviews have been elaborated in detail in Deliverable 5.1. We inductively analyzed the interviews identifying major themes within the focus topics (i.e., EUDR effectiveness and leverage points), as later shown and summarized as descriptive statistics (calculating the number of unique mentions of the major themes by the interviewees) in section 5. By making assumptions explicit, analyzing mitigating and reinforcing factors, and incorporating diverse evidence sources, our approach allowed a deeper evaluation of the plausibility and potential effectiveness of the EUDR. However, it is important also to note that our analysis contains an element of uncertainty, because the EUDR remains unimplemented until the time of conducting this research.

4 EUDR's THEORY OF CHANGE

The ultimate goal of the EUDR is defined in Art. 1 “minimizing the Union's contribution to deforestation and forest degradation worldwide”, and “thereby contributing to a reduction in global deforestation”, and “reducing the Union's contribution to greenhouse gas emissions and global biodiversity loss”. The first part reflects the ambition to clean up the sourcing patterns of EU supply chains, by prohibiting placing and making FRCs available on the EU market as well as exporting them from the EU market if they originate from newly deforested land or are otherwise not in accordance with national legislation. This intermediate goal can be objectively measured by tracking the origin of commodities imported to or produced within or exported from the EU and verifying that these have been legally produced and not in deforested or degraded areas.

The EU's contribution is minimized once no commodities originating from deforested or degraded land are imported, produced within the EU, made available on the EU market, or exported. The second part of the legally binding definition reflects an indirect, derived goal, as indicated by the word “thereby”. The EU expects that deforestation-free supply chains are a sufficient condition for “contributing” to reducing global deforestation caused by land-use change. Yet, from an analytical point of view, the necessary condition for “contributing” is the causal attribution of reduced global deforestation and degradation to the EUDR; in other words, a reduction in global deforestation that would not occur in the absence of the EUDR and is only because of the EUDR.

This second condition is arguably much harder to achieve and measure, but from a logical deductive point of view the key to reaching the third stated goal. The third goal clarifies the ultimate rationale, namely that, following the argumentation in the preamble, the protection of forests is not an intrinsic goal, but rather a necessary condition for the provision of several important ecosystem services (including carbon storage for climate regulation, soil conservation for water regulation, air purification, provision of direct use values from non-timber products, or providing non-use benefits in terms of cultural, spiritual, bequest values), the protection of biodiversity, and safeguarding of human rights, especially of indigenous and other forest-dwelling communities. In that sense, the previous two goals can be seen as intermediary, instrumental goals necessary for reaching the final one.

Along these lines, we now take the journey along the full ToC from inputs to final impacts, as depicted in Figure 1. A description of an optimistic scenario for the main EUDR effect is provided in the Figure caption. The **structure of the following subchapters** is as follows: first, we describe the respective stage in detail and what it entails optimistically (i.e., along the lines of Figure 1 caption); second, we introduce and discuss necessary conditions for (fully) reaching the stage; and third, we introduce and discuss boosters that may further contribute to the stage

beyond the main effect. Throughout the chapters, we explicitly highlight and refer to the terms in Figure 1.

Figure 1. A theory of change for the EUDR

Note: the main EUDR effect describes how inputs are linked to impacts, following an analysis of policy documents, related literature and economic theory. **Conditions** (on top) must be met for the respective next stage in the ToC to be fully achieved. **Boosters** (on the bottom) show potentials that could further improve the performance of the EUDR in moving forward (to the right-hand side) but are not directly or legally linked to the current policy implementation. In an optimistic scenario, the EUDR contributes to reduced deforestation by providing a legal framework as well as technical support and cooperation with other countries as **input**. This would result in the establishment of effective command--and-control measures, technical infrastructure, and the possibility for multiple actors to access the justice system, as a key **treatment** activity. In consequence, the direct **output** is that operators and traders would comply by no longer placing, making available or exporting commodities that are at risk of deforestation/degradation or infringing any other national laws on EU markets, at the sight of severe financial and reputational penalties. The reduced EU-demand for FRCs leads to the main **outcome**, namely that landowners restrain from future deforestation and degradation because of its lower economic profitability, normative pressure and complementary cooperation that tackles underlying causes of deforestation. Finally, the **impacts** of avoided deforestation are improvements in forest biodiversity, the provision of associated ecosystem services (ES), and returns for forest-dependent individuals and businesses.

4.1 Input: Fasten your seatbelt

The first stage in the ToC describes the formal institutional framework and enabling conditions set by an intervention (such as the EUDR). In the case of the EUDR, the **legal framework** consists of the legal Regulation (EU) 2023/1115, which defines the scope, actors and responsibilities. The EUDR restricts targeted actors in their economic activity in importing, placing and making available within the EU and exporting FRCs. It obliges them to trade only legal and deforestation-free/degradation-free commodities on the EU market, and mandates them to provide due diligence statements, including geolocation data on where the commodities were produced (Art. 3, 8, 9). Non-compliant actors face potentially severe financial penalties, including confiscation of revenues (Art. 25). The regulation also specifies the national bodies responsible for implementing, monitoring, and enforcing the regulation, namely EU Member State competent authorities. Importantly, the preamble includes the establishment of **finance mechanisms and technical assistance** for implementing enforcement, but also for support of third countries.

Regarding the scope, the regulation defines in Art. 1 relevant products that contain, have been fed with or have been made using the seven relevant FRCs: cattle, cocoa, coffee, oil palm, rubber, soy, and wood. Art. 2 further defines the targeted actors (namely operators and traders) as any natural or legal person placing or making relevant products available on the EU market or exporting them. By explicitly including traders (i.e., actors that make products available) the EUDR seeks to close an important loophole present in the EUTR. It adopts the forest definition of the FAO, namely land spanning more than 0,5 hectares with trees higher than 5 meters and a canopy cover of more than 10%. This definition has been accepted by all UN member states and thus provides a non-discriminatory legal basis. The scope is set considering the overall ambition to reduce the EU's contribution to deforestation, as the targeted commodities make up a significant share of the EU's imported deforestation footprint. At the moment, the scope is not fully comprehensive, as some important commodities such as maize are left out. Similarly, other wooded land that does not fall under the forest definition is excluded, and actors such as financial institutions involved in the supply chains of relevant commodities are left out as targeted actors. The regulatory scope can be extended in future revisions, as the EUDR contains specific provisions to review the scope periodically in terms of additional ecosystems, products or the obligations of financial institutions (Art 34). Whether or not the scope will be widened depends, among other factors, on societal and political pressure, as well as on the expected benefits for policy effectiveness and expected costs for implementation.

The EUDR holds provisions on cooperation with third countries (Art. 30), which includes **technical assistance for implementation**, partnerships, policy dialogues and participatory mechanisms to jointly address the root causes of deforestation

and forest degradation. Although responsibilities and targets are not specified, this provision can be an important pillar in shaping a global partnership approach between the EU and third countries for the sake of reducing global deforestation.

In addition to not being produced on land deforested or degraded after 2020, operators and traders must show in the due diligence statement that their FRCs also adhere to the legal standards of the respective country of production. Notably, this applies not only to commodities produced outside the EU but applies irrespective of origin also to FRCs from within the EU if they are made available on EU markets or exported from the EU. By covering all directions of commodity flows, the EUDR provides an unprecedented tool. Finally, by providing the possibility to raise substantiated concerns, actors within and beyond the EU have a new way to access justice provision about FRCs originating from EU and non-EU countries. The substantiated concerns are a key tool for actors such as businesses, NGOs, scientists, media, and others to enhance the effectiveness of the EUDR.

Now that we have clarified what the input contains, it may be worthwhile to also reflect what it does not explicitly entail. The input does not contain the existing institutions surrounding and interacting with the intervention, for example existing trade rules set by the World Trade Organization (WTO), but also previous regulations such as the EUTR. EUDR input does not include changing consumer demands and trends in trade patterns. Such contextual conditions are of course relevant and may interact with the intervention of interest in various ways but are not necessary conditions for the logic of the intervention of interest to play out. There are important moderators and complementary foundations, some of which may be grounded in complementing laws (e.g., corporate law, umbrella policies such as Farm to Fork or Biodiversity strategies and the Paris Agreement). Such contextual institutions are relevant in determining the future development and legitimacy of the EUDR. That is, they can provide the rationale for changing its scope. They also provide a communication basis for complementary regulatory efforts, for example signaling long term EU demand preferences to companies and other countries. This signaling effect could contribute to a de-facto or de-jure Brussels effect (cf. Section 4.4), in the sense that entire policy strategies ("packages") provide a stronger incentive for other countries to follow its regulation, and companies to restructure their business accordingly, than a single policy would.

Leverage points: At the input stage, the main leverage points are to widen the scope of the regulation, as already envisioned in Art. 34. For example, by including further FRCs such as maize, including further agents such as financial institutes, including other wooded land important for carbon and biodiversity. In addition, provisions on international collaboration that target the root causes of deforestation should be specified with goals and indicators.

4.2 Treatment: Pedal to the metal

The second stage in the ToC describes the exposure of actors to the new regulatory arrangement and accompanying procedures. This involves competent authorities of EU's member countries following their obligations set by the regulation by developing and implementing **command and control** measures, i.e., capacities to monitor and enforce. Treatment here refers to the monitoring and verification of policy compliance via the due diligence statements and applying sanctions where necessary. The EUDR foresees a regularly updated benchmarking system by which producer countries, both non-EU and EU countries, are classified into three deforestation and forest degradation risk categories: low-risk, standard-risk, and high-risk. The classification will be made public and can be jointly discussed with the concerned countries. It can inform content requirements for operators and traders in terms of providing due diligence statements. The regulation prescribes national authorities in EU countries to adhere to risk-based minimum inspection obligations for all levels of risk, e.g., to monitor 1% and 9% of operators placing, making available, or exporting FRCs from regions with low and high risk, respectively (Art. 16). **Penalties** include the confiscation of non-complying commodities as well as fines amounting to up to 4% of the annual turnover of the operator (Art. 25). Finally, another important procedure is the publicly available list of infringements (Art. 25). Such a "naming-and-shaming" list of companies that did not comply creates legal, normative and potentially economic disincentives for non-compliance, as it can inform public and private procurement strategies.

The EUDR enables any natural or legal person to initiate legal action, for example by raising a **substantiated concern** (Art. 31), during the stage of enforcement (treatment). This empowers interested parties such as NGOs or operators to put public and legal pressure on (competing) operators and traders placing, making available FRCs on the EU market or exporting them. Not only NGOs, but also business competitors may also have strong incentives for raising substantiated concerns, as it can help them restore competitive advantages against non-compliant operators in the marketplace. The scope of the regulation further allows substantiated concerns about FRCs not complying with national legislation and includes FRCs originating from within and outside the EU. While the risk for producing FRCs on land deforested after 2020 is relatively low in many EU countries (simply because there is no significant production of FRCs like rubber, cocoa and coffee), the risk of violating other national or EU law can be substantial for other products like timber or meat (de Vries et al., 2021). This implies, for example, that beef originating from the Netherlands must comply with national and EU law including the EU Nitrates Directive and EU Nature Restoration Law); otherwise, any actor may raise a substantiated concern. Providing proof of full legal compliance might be challenging for producers and exporters. Highly intensive livestock producing countries and regions could feel pressure to reduce nitrogen leaking into surface- and groundwaters to comply with national law. Therefore, not only operators and traders importing FRCs from non-EU countries

face additional scrutiny, but also traders of EU-originating FRCs face potential legal and financial liabilities.

In analogy with the EUTR's implementation (Köthke & Sotirov, 2024; McDermott & Sotirov, 2018), this second stage rests on the condition that sustained and **sufficient financial resources** are available and allocated. Furthermore, it requires the development of technical infrastructure and skills among competent authorities to collect and process the due diligence statements of operators and provide early warnings in case of potential infringements. The technical requirements for the monitoring system encompass not only effective and scalable information exchange with operators, but also with customs agencies, competent authorities of other Member States, and the European Commission. The implementation and enforcement of these institutional changes and associated procedures also require certainty about the long-term compatibility of the regulation with the principles of non-discrimination set by the **WTO** (Van den Bossche, 2008). Even before the EUDR's entry-into-application, the regulation has triggered strong reactions from various supply side countries, such as Indonesia and Brazil. These have challenged the EUDR's compatibility with WTO rules. The EU itself sought to achieve conformity with WTO rules by equally applying the EUDR's regulatory scope including on commodities and products produced within and outside the EU, country benchmarking etc. (Berning & Sotirov, 2023). Some ex-ante legal assessments point towards general conformity, but also highlight the need for more flexibility (Brack, 2024; Capuzzi, 2024). Along those lines, non-EU countries have argued inconsistencies and issues with WTO rules related to the EUDR's benchmarking system, for example (Azevedo-Ramos & Murakami Lima, 2024; Muradian et al., 2025). Hence, it remains uncertain what will come out of these processes and whether – and if yes, when – the EUDR can achieve de facto legal security at the international level. Non-conformity could condition the EUDR main effect; legal compatibility could boost these EUDR effects.

Certifiers can also play a role here in that they have important technical expertise in monitoring supply chains, which they can use to consult and support operators and traders in their adaptation to the EUDR. Relying on external consultants and service products to support their due diligence procedures may be cheaper for operators and traders than building these capacities on their own. In other words, certification does not exempt companies from due diligence requirements, nor does it reduce a company's liability but can be a complementary mechanism that supports these requirements. In addition, through Article 30, the European Commission and interested Member States shall assist producer countries who must produce compliant products when exporting FRCs to the EU to exchange methods (e.g., traceability systems) with one another, and through **cooperation** jointly address the root causes of deforestation. Such supportive institutions between EU and third countries/trade blocs can lend a boost to the EUDR main effect. Since the current EUDR does not specify indicators or consequences for (not) establishing such cooperations, the (dis-)incentive structure for member

states to engage in such cooperations remains unclear, which is why we do not see this pathway as a main mechanism, but rather a booster.

As alluded to earlier, the **scope** of the EUDR (e.g., in terms of commodities, biomes) can be expanded in future revisions of the regulation. Through this, the regulation's main effect could be boosted. However, this topic remains in the dark for now in terms of if and how it might be expanded. Studies could examine how the impact of the regulation could be augmented by expanding the scope in terms of commodities and biomes. It will also require future research to study the extent to which the EU can launch cooperation on EUDR relevant issues with supply side countries (North-South) and act to enable South-South cooperation. On the other hand, when it comes to certifiers supporting EUDR implementation, Deliverable 5.1 indicates that this could be the case. For example, existing voluntary sustainability schemes help timber companies to trace their supply chain to the plot of harvest, as required by the EUDR. However, the extent to which voluntary sustainability schemes will be able to technically support companies' due diligence processes and EUDR compliance will, inter alia, depend on the specific voluntary standards in question, which vary by scheme and commodity.

Leverage points: The proposed command and control measures rely on an effective, reliable, and scalable monitoring infrastructure based on technical capacities. High fixed costs related to its development could become a barrier to adopting similar command-and-control measures in other countries. Therefore, making such technical capacities openly available could support other implementers in their efforts to replicate or complement the EUDR.

4.3 Output: Engines running hot

The third stage in the ToC describes the direct, short-term, micro-level behavioral response of actors to the intervention. For the EUDR, it considers that targeted operators and traders comply with the regulatory requirements and do not place non-compliant FRCs on the EU market. Furthermore, operators and traders comply with their duties to gather information on deforestation and degradation risks in their supply chains, conduct a risk assessment and consequent risk mitigation measures and provide a due diligence statement. In consequence, FRCs are no longer placed, made available on EU the market or exported from it.

Achieving this stage assumes that intentional and non-intentional **non-compliance** remain limited to a minimum. Non-compliance by operators could involve mixing commodities from different origins, some of which could include deforested or degraded areas, and obscuring this origin by declaring false or incomplete geolocations and/or risk assessments. Such non-compliance may be intentional or non-intentional. A key condition for limited non-compliance to

materialize is effective enforcement by Member State competent authorities, because it is the credible risk of severe penalties that induces actors to incur the costs of compliance and changing their behavior. This implies conditionality on properly established capacities and infrastructure outlined in Section 4.2. Another key condition is that all competent authorities are equally well equipped and motivated to effectively monitor compliance. An asymmetrical likelihood of being caught for non-compliance could deteriorate some countries to “safe-landing havens”, where controls are less rigorous, frequent, or penalties can be circumvented.

However, available evidence indicates sizeable challenges in this regard. Deliverable 5.1 highlights several issues, such as doubts over sufficient enforcement capacities by EU Member States vis-à-vis the extensive commodity volumes to be checked, controls and penalties not being strictly enforced by the competent authorities even if sufficient capacities were available, small, opportunistic companies (with whom most non-compliance is expected) not being checked, fraud in product documentation, and some importers moving their headquarters from large to small EU Member States with presumably weaker EUDR enforcement. With the EUDR's predecessor, the EUTR, a challenge for its implementation was its uneven enforcement among the EU Member States, which opened circumvention possibilities through the import of timber via EU Member States with delayed, insufficient or weaker EUTR controls (McDermott and Sotirov, 2018; Köthke et al., 2023; Köthke and Sotirov 2024). According to the insights gained in Deliverable 5.1, the same risk still seems to apply to the EUDR. All these issues would undermine the regulatory effect of the EUDR – as elaborated in Deliverable 5.1 – removing the levelled playing field on the EU market as the main motivation for business compliance.

There are, however, also secondary mechanisms that in turn may disincentivize non-compliance. For example, NGOs or other civil society organizations can start public “**naming and shaming**” campaigns against non-complying operators, so that in addition to the direct financial penalties, there are longer-term reputational risks to branding images and losing clients. Along these lines, Greenpeace has in the context of the Brazilian Soy Moratorium put significant pressure on McDonalds for sourcing food from illegally deforested land (Ziegert & Sotirov, 2024). Such normative pressure is directly stimulated by the EUDR in two ways; first, via the public “naming and shaming” list of infringements, and second, via the improved technical monitoring capabilities and traceability infrastructure to be established around the due diligence procedures. Public campaigns can even go beyond naming and shaming non-compliance and establish a boosting effect beyond the original scope of the EUDR. They can call out companies' double standards, for example if companies continue to place FRCs from risky origins on other, less regulated markets, or if they place non-regulated commodities from cleared other wooded biomes on EU markets. Although such behavior would be compliant with the EUDR, it creates doubt about companies' commitments to tackle the root causes of deforestation and degradation, which

can interact with consumer preferences for sustainable production and thereby decrease demand for that company's products.

An additional dimension of publicly naming and shaming non-compliance may not be directly related to deforestation, but the legality requirement regarding other national laws. The enhanced traceability of certain commodities in combination with a wider range of actors that can raise substantiated concerns can enable better identification of legal infringements, for example of the Nitrates and Habitats Directives or other national laws also within the EU.

Regarding boosters acting through civil society, Deliverable 5.1 suggests that it may have mixed influence. Normative pressure that is exercised through civil society campaigning is more likely to affect stock companies (that have shareholders to respond to) and consumer-facing and large companies and brands that are exposed to the public. Other companies, such as SMEs, may be less susceptible to it. Thus, civil society campaigning on deforestation related issues can be expected to affect only some companies. Adding to this, findings in Deliverable 5.1 suggest that the European Commission's prospective publication of non-compliant businesses as part of the EUDR will motivate business compliance. However, for the time being, it is unknown how this will play out. These findings are also in line with previous research that finds rather the bigger companies to have better complied with the EUTR than SMEs, given their better knowledge of the legal provisions, technical, financial and human capacities, the normative and reputational pressure built by NGOs and media, and underlying values of rule of law and sustainability (Köthke and Sotirov 2024)

In a similar way, the role of independent, voluntary third-party **labelling** interacts with both EUDR compliance and can serve as an effective communication vehicle for companies' ambitions to go beyond EUDR requirements, establishing a boosting effect. That is, sustainability labels continue to play a role in informing consumers about companies' practices such as driving deforestation and degradation beyond the scope of the EUDR, but also regarding human rights, biodiversity and carbon storage as superior goals of the EUDR.

However, in this regard it is also important to note limitations of voluntary schemes, such as lack of independence of auditors (who check compliance with voluntary schemes), deforestation spillovers into non-certified areas, or in some cases negative effects on socio-economic indicators (Garrett et al., 2021; Heilmayr et al., 2020; Karsenty, 2019; Piketty & Garcia Drigo, 2018). Furthermore, depending on the commodity and context, adoption in general of such schemes by companies can be limited (Karsenty, 2019). As indicated in Deliverable 5.1, only companies with sustainability high in their internal values and reflected in their cultural-cognitive motivations are more likely to adopt certification than others. While voluntary certification schemes may in some of their aspects and scope go beyond the EUDR (e.g., in terms of social requirements), they fall short in providing a comprehensive prohibition of

deforestation and forest degradation and are insufficient to demonstrate compliance with the EUDR (Cosimo, 2023). Hence, a boosting effect by third-party certification schemes may remain limited.

Leverage points: Authorities must be equipped with sufficient financial and technical resources to exert a credible risk of penalties for non-compliance. Early warning systems of deforestation risks that integrate a wide range of data sources may contribute to effective monitoring. Some operators and traders may require support or further incentives for implementation to reduce the risk of them leaving EU markets and thereby decreasing EU trade leverage.

4.4 Outcomes: Rubber hits the road

The fourth stage in the ToC describes intermediate multilevel system response to the intervention. For the EUDR, it describes the changes in land use on the ground resulting from the regulation. The EUDR does not impose direct restrictions on landowners or land managers, but only on operators and traders that source from them. It is therefore important to understand how a fully and effectively implemented previous stage of deforestation-free supply chains into and out of the EU would translate towards land use decisions. Specifically, how it relates to future land use decisions, since the goal of the EUDR is to avoid deforestation and forest degradation, i.e., the future clearing of forested land and/or conversion of primary forests to plantations or planted/logged over forests.

From an economic perspective, the decision on clearing or degrading forested land depends, next to considerations of legality, on the profitability of this option vis-à-vis other land use options and income possibilities. That is, for the EUDR to influence land use decisions, it must either raise the rents of standing forest or reduce the rents of deforestation and forest degradation (Angelsen, 2010). The EUDR provides no direct economic mechanism for increasing rents to standing forests, but we will turn to potential indirect mechanisms later. From an economic theory perspective, there are potentially four main pathways through which the EUDR could influence land use decisions:

1. **Direct reforestation pathway:** Land deforested between the EUDR temporal cutoff (31.12.2020) and implementation phase (currently set to 30.12.2025) for EU-bound commodity production will be abandoned and grow back into secondary forests.
2. **Direct avoided deforestation pathway:** Land planned to be deforested after 2025 for EU-bound commodity exports will no longer be cleared.
3. **Direct avoided forest degradation pathway:** Timber planned to be harvested in primary forests in a way non-compliant with the EUDR after 2025 for EU exports will no longer be harvested.
4. **Indirect avoided deforestation pathway:** Planned or already deforested land for EU-bound commodity exports will now need to serve non-EU

commodity markets – with lower prices and lower profits on average – thus reducing average returns to, and hence amounts of, deforestation.

The first pathway (1) is unlikely to happen because the land clearing investment has already been made, so land managers would face sunk costs or costs of income forgone if not diverting their production to less restricted markets (e.g., China, or local markets in Brazil) or switching production to commodities outside the scope of the EUDR (e.g., maize). From an economic point of view, there are several relevant conditions to the remaining three pathways (2-4), the most important one being that **spillover effects** such as evasion via market segregation and leakage to unregulated domains remain limited (more on leakage in Section 4.5). This forms a crucial condition. We introduce these spillover effects, their mechanisms and determinants of their magnitude in detail in Deliverable 5.2, so here we just provide a brief overview.

Policy **evasion** refers to an adaptive strategy of operators to **segregate** products depending on their origin either to the EU market or to other, less restrictive markets. Evasion becomes more likely when the costs of EUDR-compliance are high compared to the costs of segregation. The costs of segregation depend on regional supply chain characteristics, including available infrastructure suitable for segregation, but also other factors that influence how stable relations between producers and traders are over time. The interplay of such factors is difficult to observe, but the resulting stability in trading relations has been conceptualized and operationalized as supply side stickiness (Reis et al., 2020). Examples can be seen along many supply chains, for example deforestation-free soy from Brazil is already before the EUDR mostly consumed in Europe, while uncertified soy is consumed domestically or exported to China. To the extent that evasion via commodity- and market segregation is possible, pathways (2) and (3) mentioned above become unrealistic, since land managers and traders can simply divert products to alternative demand destinations. Deliverables 5.1 and 5.2 find that the market segregation of exports may vary depending on the supply chain context. For example, for some commodities like wood pulp establishing physical infrastructure for segregation along the supply chain is impractical or even impossible. For others, like soy, segregation is expected, although it will not come without its challenges, including cost increases. In timber supply chains, presence or absence of segregation may depend on various variables, such as voluntary certification status of a company, ownership of one versus multiple forest concessions, and private commitments of companies.

The last pathway (4), on the other hand, depends largely on the market power of the EU and the extent to which a drop in its demand can influence global commodity prices. That is, for commodities for which the EU-imports make up a high **market share**, the elimination of demand for these commodities from deforested or degraded land after 2020 leads to lower prices, since excess supply is not fully met by other demand sides. If on the other hand the market share is low, the demand can easily be picked up by other destination markets.

Therefore, the main mechanism is decreasing the rent of forest conversion, namely by effectively eliminating the demand for FRCs produced on land deforested after 2020 and via the reduced demand also decrease its price and producer profitability. However, the lower the EU market share, the more prone to evasion a supply chain becomes. Arguably, this will be the key single obstacle in moving from allegedly “clean EU supply chains” towards “significantly lower deforestation and forest degradation globally”.

A final condition concerns EUDR's **coherence** with other policies and governance mechanisms, particularly on the supply side. As introduced in Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2, the regulatory landscape is already populated by numerous policies and governance mechanisms governing legal and sustainable FRC supply chains, each with their own intervention logic. The arrival of the EUDR will create interactions with these other, pre-existing instruments. These interactions could give birth to policy incoherence, meaning that the goals, instruments and/or practices from different regulations work against each other, in major contradiction. In such a case, with the EUDR possibly compromising the goals achievement of other domestic regulations, it could undermine its broader intended outcomes (reduced future land conversion) and raise legitimacy concerns. On the contrary, the EUDR can also lead to policy coherence with already existing national and transnational regulatory instruments. This will boost the EUDR's effectiveness.

Concerning the EUDR's (in)coherence with other policies and governance mechanisms, Deliverable 4.3 observes how the very regulatory design of the EUDR and other, pre-existing instruments could lead to policy incoherence. As such, the EUDR could negatively impact and delegitimize governance strategies already underway in supply-side countries (e.g., public policies and private sector arrangements). Legitimacy problems caused by the EUDR as a unilateral intervention have also been highlighted by Muradian et al. (2025). Overall, these issues could produce unintended consequences in terms of undermining the effects of other policies and governance mechanisms.

In sum, the complex interplay of multiple conditions beyond the direct control of the EU (global markets and regional supply chain characteristics) turn this stage into a potential point of critical (partial) ineffectiveness of the EUDR. On a more positive outlook, however, there are also important boosters that can occur at this stage.

On the one hand, a **de-facto Brussels effect** describes the process by which multinational companies adhere to stricter regulations beyond the scope of its application (Bradford, 2012, 2020). This would be the case when operators facing high costs of commodity and market segregation decide to comply with the EUDR, but also use the compliance standard for non-EU markets. One reason to do this could be high costs of commodity and market segregation. Another reason could be an improved public image, also because of public shaming

campaigns highlighted in Section 4.2. Furthermore, companies may expect EUDR-like regulations to be adopted in other important markets, whereby early business-wide compliance can offer long-term advantages.

Relatedly, a **de-jure Brussels effect** describes the process by which other countries follow the strict EU regulation standards and employ similar legal frameworks to regulate supply chains of relevant commodities. This can be motivated, among other factors, by the political and normative power the EU imposes. It can also be caused by civil society and companies lobbying for stricter regulation; the former because of societal preferences, the latter because they fear competitive disadvantages. Both the de-facto and de-jure Brussels effect are similar in their outcome to an increase in the EU market share. That is because they lead to a relative increase in demand for deforestation-free commodities, while reducing the remaining opportunities for evasion.

Conditions under which Brussels effect is possible include a relatively large (EU) market; political willingness and strong regulatory capacity to adopt, develop and enforce standards; the predisposition to regulate inelastic targets (i.e., targets that cannot flee due to increases in regulatory stringency, such as consumer markets); and a high non-divisibility element (i.e., companies find it technically, legally or economically hard to separate products destined for different markets and, therefore, prefer to streamline their operations according to a common set of standards) (Bastos Lima & Schilling-Vacaflor, 2024; Vasconcelos et al., 2024).

However, a de-jure Brussels effect may be unlikely to happen at least in the short term (Bastos Lima & Schilling-Vacaflor, 2024; Vasconcelos et al., 2024). For example, China is expected to not adopt EUDR-like standards due to its foreign policy stance of non-interference and concerns about its food security. As noted in Deliverable 5.1, a more likely avenue may be a de-facto Brussels effect, that is, that some businesses in third countries start adhering to and conducting EUDR-aligned due diligence (even without changes in the respective national regulatory context). For instance, Chinese timber companies have sought efforts to produce products compliant with the EUTR (Nathan et al., 2018). However, more evidence is needed to generate an understanding of this and to what extent it may happen. Regarding a de jure Brussels effect through transnational policy diffusion, knowledge transfer and institutional isomorphism, based on an efficient application of Article 30, different initiatives have been put into place, such as the 'Forest Partnerships', 'Team Europe Initiative' and 'The Sustainable Agriculture for Forest Ecosystems (SAFE) Project', with the intent to support the implementation of the EUDR in producer countries. Yet, it is too early to report on concrete evidence, as their effectiveness is also still to be seen. Evidence from previous work on the EU's Forest Law Enforcement, Governance and Trade (FLEGT) VPAs processes provide some evidence of the possibility of the Brussels effect but also the scope conditions and challenges to achieve it (Carodenuto et al., 2024; Polo Villanueva et al., 2023).

On the positive side, legislation on forest-risk commodities is being considered in other countries such as the US with the US FOREST Act¹, the UK with the UK Environmental Bill² (Villoria et al., 2022), or is already in force such as in Australia with the 2012 Illegal Logging Prohibition Act³, or Japan with the 2017 Clean Wood Act⁴. This indicates a global trend towards regulating the sourcing of these commodities. However, the US and UK laws contain lower-level standards (compared to the EUDR), allowing imports from legal deforestation in line with national laws.

Leverage points: The Brussels effect(s) are supported by investments in technical monitoring infrastructure and capacity building, both on the side of competent authorities as well as on the side of operators and traders. There is also the opportunity for a 'smart policy mix' between the EUDR and domestic regulations given, for example, its legality requirement. Boosting can happen if Article 30 is taken seriously to understand and find a balance between the already existing initiatives and needs of supply-side producer countries and the EU countries.

4.5 Impact: Only the sky is the limit

The fifth and final stage in the ToC describes long-term macro-level changes towards the intervention's ultimate goal. This is where different policy tools' effectiveness can and should be compared against each other. As mentioned previously, the main motivation for protecting forests from deforestation and forest degradation are the derived benefits for biodiversity and human health, or the provision of ecosystem services including carbon storage for climate regulation, soil conservation for water regulation, air purification, provision of direct use values from non-timber products, or providing non-use benefits in terms of cultural, spiritual, bequest values. In many situations, a reduction in deforestation and degradation will lead to improvements in these overarching goal dimensions. But there are once more important conditions and potential barriers for the overall goals to materialize.

Most importantly, land use **leakage** must remain limited. Leakage is also an indirect spillover effect, but different from evasion: it refers to the indirect displacement of activities causing deforestation. For example, if soy is no longer being grown on recently deforested land but elsewhere, it can displace other crops such as maize, which in turn become drivers of deforestation. Leakage becomes more likely whenever access to suitable land is unconstrained and

¹ <https://www.congress.gov/bill/118th-congress/senate-bill/3371/text>

² <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2021/30/schedule/17>

³ <https://www.legislation.gov.au/C2012A00166/latest/text>

⁴ <https://www.rinya.maff.go.jp/j/riyou/goho/english/english-index.html>

competitive, production factor mobility is high, and demand elasticity is high (which goes hand in hand with a low EU market share).

Note that all forms of leakage are fully compliant with the EUDR, that is, they can occur under completely deforestation-free supply chains. Activity leakage can occur to forests via the spatial displacement of non-targeted commodities, as discussed in Section 4.4. But it can also occur across other domains, for example when the production of relevant commodities is shifted to other wooded land or non-wooded land, constituting a condition. While such shifts are no longer classified as “deforestation”, because the affected biome is not considered forest, they can still imply significant impacts to biodiversity, ecosystem services and net carbon emissions. For example, the *Cerrado* region adjacent to the Amazon is rich in species, while peatlands in Indonesia contain more carbon in the soil than many forests. Both could be affected by leakage into non-forest areas and may ultimately condition the net policy impacts. Therefore, a key moderator that determines the severity of leakage between outcome to impact is the distribution and density of the targeted outcome (carbon stocks per hectare, species, ...) in areas suitable for leakage.

Empirical studies on leakage of related policies suggest that these effects can reach significant magnitudes and potentially offset large parts of an intervention's net gain. For example, regarding leakage into other woody biomes, Villoria et al. (2022) showed that domestic leakage offsets 43-50% of the avoided deforestation induced by existing and proposed zero-deforestation supply chain policies in Brazil's soy sector. However, more research is needed to understand how the EUDR impacts such leakage dynamics. For a detailed review of other studies on land use spillovers, we refer to CLEVER Deliverable 5.2.

Furthermore, spillovers beyond land use can occur and condition policy effectiveness to the extent that they relate to the policy goals. Existing supply chains are typically set in a competitive environment, with an eye to minimizing transport and storage costs. But the EUDR and associated shifts in regional demands can result in changes in supply chains transport routes. Based on insights from Deliverable 5.2, the EUDR could result in shifts in some trade flows and routes, such as with the soy supply chain in Brazil. Soy exports going to the EU decreased significantly from the southern routes (Paranaguá and Santos joint port exports dropped from 12.6 million tons in 2004 to 5.24 million tons in 2020) and increased from the northern routes (Manaus and Santarém joint port exports increased from 1.26 million tons in 2004 to 4.29 million tons in 2020) (Reis & Prada Moro, 2022; Trase, 2024). Products from southern states of Brazil (Rio Grande do Sul, Paraná) have lower risk of deforestation and could therefore be exported to the EU, while products from the Amazon region are redirected to other markets. This would imply longer transportation distances, and associated release of CO₂ emissions if the transport via trucks and ships is not free of emissions.

Owing to the complexity of global commodity trade, it is difficult to predict how such dynamics would play out in a wider commodity context. Here, future modeling studies could provide valuable insights. In sum, even under completely deforestation-free supply chains and no land use leakage, the policies' impact on carbon emissions could be conditioned via secondary **transport emission** sources.

Finally, the policy can have unintended consequences detrimental to socioeconomic goals. Specifically, producers are heterogeneous and affected to different extents by the regulation. Some may be well-equipped to provide the required geolocation data, while others may not. The preamble describes intentions to safeguard smallholder producers and indigenous communities, but they have generally fewer resources to comply with information demands for the due diligence statement than large scale producers. In other words, it may be costlier and riskier for operators and traders to engage with smallholders.

Deliverables 5.1 and 5.2 reported on perceptions and self-reports about smallholders generally facing higher costs of compliance with the EUDR, and more challenges in providing information requested by operators. As a result, operators tend to simplify their sourcing patterns, which entails excluding smallholders from their supply chains. This compliance cost gradient can exacerbate existing division in supply chains, where some supply side market actors have access to the EU market while others are mainly connected to domestic or other export markets with lower legality and deforestation-free standards. However, the marginalization of these producers could in some cases contribute to the "root causes of deforestation", that the EUDR envisions to combat via collaborative approaches. It therefore remains crucial that adequate **support for smallholder** producers and other forest-dwelling communities is provided, at least to cover their marginally higher costs of compliance. This can, in turn, boost the EUDR's main effect. The literature has earlier identified these as potential unintended consequences of the EUDR (O'Brien et al., 2022; Zhunusova et al., 2022). Whether these materialize will also in part depend on whether EU businesses follow the obligations and spirit of the regulation, particularly around supporting smallholders through capacity building and investments as part of their risk mitigation, as outlined in the EUDR (Art. 11).

Leverage points: Widening the scope (forest definition, commodities, actors) can reduce leakage potentials. Smallholders' elevated compliance costs must be compensated to avoid marginalization as a possible root driver of deforestation.

5 STAKEHOLDER INTERVIEWS

5.1 Actor perceptions of EUDR effectiveness

Complementing the above analysis of the EUDR's ToC, we present here our primary source derived findings on actor perceptions of EUDR (in)effectiveness and reasons behind it. Specifically, interviewees were asked the following question: "How effective will the EUDR become in reducing global deforestation, forest degradation, and associated human rights violations, and what are the main challenges and opportunities for its effectiveness?". Figure 2 displays an overview of actors' perceptions of EUDR effectiveness (n=111). 77 (or 69%) of the interviewees were from the supply-side and 34 (or 31%) from the demand-side. Only 15% of the interviewees believed the EUDR to be effective once implemented. A significantly larger proportion (44%) believed it to be ineffective, painting a more pessimistic picture of its potential. Roughly the same share of interviewees (41%), on the other hand, saw the EUDR's future effectiveness as mixed, meaning that it could be either effective or ineffective depending on various factors.

Figure 2. Overview of actor perceptions of EUDR effectiveness at the global level (n=123)

In terms of reasons for which actors believed the EUDR to be effective, only one reason was mainly raised. This was an EUDR global knock-on effect (mentioned eight times)⁵, implying that the arrival and implementation of the EUDR would set a trend for other markets to adopt similar regulations. This, in turn, would lead to a global level effect that would be far more impactful than what the EUDR and the EU market alone could achieve. This evidence supports the expectations of the possibility to see the "Brussels effect" at work which is among the key boosters in the EUDR ToC.

⁵ 10 observations are not included nor reported in more detail here. These include reasons that were uniquely mentioned only once or twice and mentions where interviewees did not specify a reasons or their stated reason was unclear.

In Figure 3, we present reasons for the EUDR's ineffectiveness.⁶ The top-cited reasons were “leakage/market shift/segregation” (20 mentions) and “small EU market share” (19 mentions), corresponding to the conditions on market segregation and leakage in the ToC. Interviewees also mentioned in 10 cases that the EUDR does not affect all deforestation, such as deforestation driven by mining, land speculation, subsistence agriculture, or consumption by domestic markets, all of which would lower its effectiveness. Similarly often, definitional aspects in the EUDR were seen as too narrowly set, for instance in terms of its cutoff date perceived as too late or the definition of forest that excludes biodiversity-rich biomes. While future revisions of the EUDR could address some of these shortcomings (e.g., definitional aspects) as reflected in the booster “widening future EUDR scope”, others (e.g., deforestation driven by land speculation or subsistence agriculture) may stay out of reach for the EUDR, unless the EUDR is supported by appropriate complementary measures that could help foster change beyond the targeted supply chains. Interviewees also mentioned in seven cases the EUDR's incoherence with existing policies and measures on the supply side (e.g., Amazon Soy Moratorium) as a reason for its ineffectiveness, which is also reflected in the condition “EUDR is coherent with pre-existing policies and governance mechanisms”.

Figure 3. Reasons for perceived EUDR ineffectiveness. Numbers refer to unique mentions of a reason

Further reasons for EUDR ineffectiveness were “complexity of supply chains and deforestation” (5 mentions), “EUDR unilaterally designed/imposed” (5 mentions), and “EUDR lacks support/incentives” (4 mentions).

⁶ 13 observations are not included nor reported in more detail here. These include reasons that were uniquely mentioned only once or twice and mentions where interviewees did not specify a reasons or their stated reason was unclear.

Finally, Figure 4 displays reasons for mixed views by interviewees on the EUDR's effectiveness.⁷ The most highlighted point (17 mentions) was that EUDR effectiveness depends on regulatory alignment with and political support by other countries. On the one hand, this means that only if other countries (e.g., China) adopt similar regulations can EUDR be expected to be effective. We highlighted this already above in relation to the booster "Brussels effect". On the other hand, interviewees stressed that if producing countries do not politically endorse and support the EUDR and its implementation – due to a prevalent feeling among them that the EUDR was unilaterally designed and imposed by the EU – the EUDR will be ineffective. We also highlight this aspect in the EUDR ToC as the booster "supportive institutions between EU and third countries/trade blocks", and the legitimacy issue has additionally been raised by Muradian et al. (2025). The second most cited reason (13 mentions) was that the EUDR's effectiveness depends on supply chain segregation, market shifts, and EU market share of a commodity, which is similar to the most cited reason for EUDR (in-)effectiveness earlier. The only difference is that here, interviewees approached the aspect from a more conditional perspective, noting that if the conditions are favourable (e.g., as they might be in the global cocoa supply chain), the EUDR can be effective. Furthermore, interviewees mentioned in seven cases that EUDR effectiveness depends on the commodity or sector, and whether deforestation is driven by markets or subsistence agriculture. For example, interviewees said that deforestation does not exist for years already in the wood pulp sector in Brazil, which is why the EUDR would have no effect there. Also, interviewees pointed out that the EUDR could have an effect on deforestation driven by markets but not on deforestation driven by subsistence agriculture (cf. "EUDR doesn't affect all deforestation" above as a reason for ineffectiveness).

Figure 4. Reasons for EUDR effectiveness perceived as mixed. Numbers refer to unique mentions of a reason

⁷ 17 observations are not included nor reported in more detail here. These include reasons that were uniquely mentioned only once or twice and mentions where interviewees did not specify a reason or their stated reason was unclear.

Interviewees observed in six cases that there is simply a lot of uncertainty in attempting to predict the EUDR's effectiveness and in three cases that EUDR effectiveness is contingent on enforcement in the EU, which corresponds to the condition "administrative capacity in the EU is sufficient", something that has been explored in the EUTR implementation which the EUDR is building on (McDermott and Sotirov 2018; Köthke and Sotirov 2024). Interviewees also pointed out in three cases that the effectiveness depends on the timeframe (e.g., the EUDR could be effective in the long-term but not in the short-term).

In summary, our exploration of actor perceptions of EUDR effectiveness revealed that most interviewees perceive the EUDR's potential effectiveness rather critically than positively. This may be – at least partly – due to an overrepresentation of interviewees from the supply-side, who may be more inclined to view the EUDR critically than positively. The reasons for the interviewees' views largely correspond to the various "breaking and making points" (i.e., the conditions and boosters) identified in the EUDR ToC. This provides support for our EUDR ToC and confirms the critical aspects along the change logic that should be addressed if policymakers, strategists and consultants wanted to enhance the effects of the EUDR along the different ToC steps. Correspondingly, in the next section, we turn our attention to identifying leverage points along international non-food biomass supply chains beyond the EUDR context.

5.2 Actor-specific leverage points for transformative change

We expand here our exploration of leverage points⁸ for transformative change to a wider context, also beyond the EUDR. This is important for several reasons. The EUDR as a supply chain regulation targets international trade, but a limited amount of 20-25% of agriculture-driven deforestation is for export demand, the rest serving domestic demand (Pendrell et al., 2022). For example, in the Brazilian Legal Amazon, the domestic market is responsible for almost triple the deforestation generated by international demand (Haddad et al., 2024). Furthermore, a single instrument like the EUDR cannot be expected to address all issues facing the legality and sustainability of FRC supply chains. Rather, a mix of international, EU and national public policies and market-driven governance tools is needed to secure legal and sustainable supply chains contributing to deforestation and degradation reduction worldwide (Börner et al., 2020; Gunningham & Grabosky, 1998; Sotirov et al., 2022; Williamson & Lynch-Wood, 2021). For example, the EUDR focuses on the supply chain, but territorial approaches (e.g., at jurisdictional or landscape levels) can be better suited for addressing more complex land use dynamics beyond the bounds of a supply chain (zu Ermgassen et al., 2024). Since silver bullet solutions do not exist, what could a transnational demand side measure like the EUDR be combined with for a greater chance at achieving transformative change?

Against this context, we gathered actors' views on what or where the most important leverage points for conserving biodiversity and reducing deforestation and forest degradation are. Table 1 presents an overview of their responses, including whether the leverage points are to be tackled on the supply (e.g., Brazil, Cameroon, Gabon) or demand (e.g., the EU) side of supply chains, as indicated by the interviewees (n=141). 105 (or 74%) of the interviewees were from the supply-side and 36 (or 26%) from the demand-side. The table also displays the mechanism and type of the leverage points. For mechanisms, an incentive mechanism indicates facilitation of trade and, generally, market creating "positive" measures, whereas disincentives create constraints to illegality in business and expansion of illegal production. Enabling factors facilitate various conditions that can help ensure good governance and legality and/or sustainability of production and consumption.

For a total of 39 mentions, interviewees raised the need for ensuring monitoring and enforcement for legal compliance as the top-cited leverage point. A clear majority of these mentions were addressed to the supply side (i.e., non-EU countries). This also indicates that insufficient implementation of laws of countries of production is still one of the key drivers of deforestation and degradation. These suggestions also stress an understanding that "fixing" the legal enforcement issues would create the most impact. Likewise, and in relation to

⁸ As defined in section 3, leverage points are places within a complex system where a small shift in one thing can produce big changes in everything.

the demand side (i.e., the EU), interviewees mainly stressed the importance of ensuring effective monitoring and enforcement of the EUDR.

Table 1. Leverage points, their mechanism, type, and location in the supply chain for conserving biodiversity and reducing deforestation and forest degradation (number of interviewees=141; number of observations=298). The numbers in the table refer to unique mentions of a leverage point across supply chain locations⁹ Leverage point location indicates whether the leverage points are to be tackled on the supply (e.g., Brazil, Cameroon, Gabon) or demand (e.g., the EU) side of supply chains, as indicated by the interviewees

Leverage point	Leverage point mechanism	Leverage point type	Leverage point location across supply chains				
			Supply	Demand	Both	Unspecified/unclear	Total
Ensure monitoring & enforcement for legal compliance	Disincentive	Area based	30	6	1	2	39
Positive economic & market incentives	Incentive	Supply chain based	15	17	3	2	37
Strengthen & support local capacities (technical, technological, etc.)	Incentive	Area based	22	1	2	6	31
Collaboration & partnerships; political will	Enabling factors	Other	10	13	4	3	30
Clarify land tenure & policy; address land grabbing & speculation	Enabling factors	Area based	22	0	0	1	23
Brussels effect (vis-à-vis EUDR)	Enabling factors	Other	1	14	4	2	21
Payments for ecosystem services (PES)	Incentive	Area based	14	1	0	0	15
Fight corruption	Disincentive	Other	8	0	0	1	9
Regulate the financial sector vis-à-vis deforestation	Enabling factors	Other	4	0	0	5	9

⁹ 32 observations are not included nor reported in more detail here. These include leverage points that were uniquely mentioned only once or twice and leverage points for which it was unclear what the interviewees were describing.

Address criminal networks in connection to deforestation ¹⁰	Enabling factors	Other	8	0	0	1	9
Strong traceability system; improve information & transparency in supply chains	Enabling factors	Supply chain based	5	0	3	0	8
Support local populations & develop economic opportunities	Enabling factors	Area based	8	0	0	0	8
Revise & strengthen regulatory frameworks	Enabling factors	Area based	7	0	0	0	7
Promote voluntary certification	Incentive	Supply chain based	4	1	1	1	7
Mindset change	Enabling factors	Other	4	0	0	3	7
Raise awareness of the economic value of conserving & managing forests	Enabling factors	Other	4	2	0	1	7
Measures on domestic markets & consumption	Enabling factors	Other	4	0	1	0	5
Implement regenerative agricultural practices	Enabling factors	Area based	5	0	0	0	5
Forest landscape restoration	Enabling factors	Area based	4	0	0	0	4
Lower the consumption of commodities	Enabling factors	Other	0	3	1	0	4
Reconcile development with preservation	Enabling factors	Other	4	0	0	0	4
Strengthen science-policy interface	Enabling factors	Other	1	0	0	2	3
Ensure coherence of policies & initiatives	Enabling factors	Other	2	0	0	1	3

¹⁰ Relates to addressing unpunished environmental crimes such as organized crime networks involved in drug trafficking, illegal mining, illegal logging, and smuggling.

Expand protected areas	Disincentive	Area based	3	0	0	0	3
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The provision of positive economic and market incentives was the second most mentioned leverage point (37 mentions), divided relatively equally between supply and demand sides. In relation to the supply side, interviewees mainly mentioned domestic incentive schemes. An example can be raised from Gabon, where forest concessionaires that are sustainability certified pay just half the amount of the hectare-based area fee on their concessions compared to non-certified forest concessionaires. Another common argument is the need to leverage deforestation and forest degradation reduction through sustainable financing. In particular, it was often suggested that financial institutions (e.g., banks, investors) should condition their loans to companies on basis of the environmental considerations (e.g., deforestation-free) of the companies. In relation to the demand side, interviewees said, mainly in connection to timber trade, that the price paid by the European market should be higher so that producers in tropical countries would be more incentivized to seek access to the EU market and respect its standards.

After a gap in the number of mentions of the top-2 cited leverage points, the third most mentioned leverage point (31 mentions) was strengthening and supporting local capacities (e.g., technical and technological), the majority of which was indicated for the supply side. This included various issues, such as supporting forest inventory, developing timber processing, supporting civil society, and aiding local communities. It was also said by five interviewees that there should be direct, unconditional support (e.g., financial) from the EU side for actors in the supply side countries to help adjust to regulations like the EUDR.

Fourth, a leverage point connecting political will on the one hand and collaboration and partnerships on the other hand was mentioned 30 times, divided fairly equally between the supply and demand sides. For the supply side, the essential argument was that without political will, little effective actions (e.g., revision and implementation of domestic laws) are taken in the countries. Hence, political will is needed, as well as collaboration among all national actors. For the demand side, it was mainly highlighted that in relation to regulations like the EUDR, the EU should adopt a collaborative partnership approach with actors on the supply side to secure political will there for supportive implementation. Otherwise, political will on the supply side cannot be secured for policy implementation.

After another gap in the number of mentions of the third and fourth most cited leverage points, three more leverage points stand out in the descriptive statistics. The fifth most mentioned leverage point (23 mentions) was about clarifying land tenure and land policy and addressing land grabbing and land speculation. This was nearly fully indicated for the supply side. Two arguments within this leverage point stood out: on the one hand, deforestation is a complex issue that needs cross-sectoral solutions, which is why comprehensive land use planning and policy is needed. On the other hand, deforestation is not always driven directly because of commodity production, but rather because of land speculation,

which needs resolving along with related tenure clarity and security. The sixth most mentioned leverage point (21 mentions) was the Brussels effect in relation to the EUDR. This was mainly indicated for the demand side, meaning that other demand side markets should and could adopt EUDR-like regulations and standards with the EU “showing the way” initially. The seventh most cited leverage point (15 mentions) was payments for ecosystem services (PES), which was nearly fully indicated for the supply side. PES was raised mainly in relation to ecosystem services beyond the focal commodities under examination (soy, timber, and wood pulp), such as non-timber forest products, biodiversity, or carbon, and hence to make trees and forests more valuable standing than cut down.

A variety of further leverage points were raised by the interviewees, each of them with less than 10 mentions. These included regulating the financial sector on deforestation, revising and strengthening regulatory frameworks, promoting voluntary certification, addressing measures on domestic markets and consumption, and ensuring policy coherence. For the most part, these leverage points were addressed to the supply side, indicating a crucial role for supply side measures in conserving biodiversity and reducing deforestation and forest degradation.

Figure 5 further displays an overview of the mechanism and type of the leverage points. Just over a half (53%) of the leverage points can be characterized as enabling factors, indicating a preference by actors for addressing issues at the level of foundational conditions. About a third (30%) of the leverage points are incentive based and 17% are disincentive based. Between these two, interviewees, thus, voted more for “positive” than “negative” signals as leverage points. When it comes to leverage point type, area-based leverage points (i.e., usually delimited by clear geographic boundaries) made up 45% of all leverage points, whereas supply chain-based leverage points represented only 18% of the total. This implies comparatively lower recognition or preference for transnational governance measures. The remaining leverage points constituted 37% of the total.

Figure 5. Mechanism (left) and type (right) of leverage points

When interpreting the role of actors in relation to the different leverage points, two overarching observations can be made. First, most leverage points (62% in total) were indicated for the supply side. This speaks about the importance of supply side measures and the role that supply side actors have in creating transformative change. It also underscores the crucial aspect of international collaboration, so that supply and demand side actors can work together to address issues and challenges. Second, public actors have a sole or key role in many of the most-mentioned leverage points, such as ensuring monitoring and enforcement, political will, clarifying land tenure and land policy, the Brussels effect, and revising regulatory frameworks. As such, it can be essential to seek ways to exploit these leverage points, having a leading role by public actors whilst ensuring the inclusion of other actors in processes.

6 DISCUSSION

Our examination of the EUDR's ToC and its underlying assumptions exposed several limitations that potentially could make the EUDR ineffective in achieving its intended effects, at different levels. For outputs, it is more than uncertain whether the administrative capacity in all EU countries would suffice to ensure strict monitoring and enforcement of the complex requirements. For outcomes, significant market segregation will likely take place for most commodities, due to the EU's small and declining global market shares. For impacts, it appears plausible that the EUDR's implementation will result in some leakage into ecosystems not covered by its regulatory scope. Moreover, important boosters like the Brussels effect may lend only limited aid at least in the short-term, although long-term trends are possible but difficult to predict. At the same time, several leverage points exist along the ToC that could enhance the EUDR's effectiveness.

First, to make the regulation more effective, its scope could be expanded to include more products (like maize) and actors (such as financial institutions), and international collaboration should be supported. Second, a good monitoring system is key and sharing it with other countries can help them adopt similar yet customized measures. Third, authorities need enough resources to enforce the rules and penalize those who do not comply. Some businesses may need help to implement the regulation, so they do not leave the EU market. Fourth, investing in monitoring and capacity building can create a "Brussels effect," where other countries adopt similar regulations. A "smart policy mix" between the EUDR and domestic laws in supply-side countries can also be beneficial. Fifth, widening the scope of the EUDR can reduce leakage potentials, and there is a need to support smallholders to avoid negative impacts on them.

Furthermore, our stakeholder interviews-based exploration of leverage points for conserving biodiversity and reducing deforestation and forest degradation beyond the EUDR revealed multiple such points. A common feature of many leverage points is that they are indicated for the supply side and the main actor behind them should be the public sector. Hence, from an EU perspective, it is crucial to engage with supply side countries in a collaborative partnership approach, building trust and political will to address the challenges and perceived environment-development trade-offs that often coexist with them. Transformative change is more likely to be achieved when collaboration is facilitated to exploit multiple leverage points for mutual gain between the EU and partner countries.

Moreover, the report reiterates that the EUDR is a trade-centric policy that does not address the broader historical and structural challenges of deforestation in tropical countries. Therefore, those challenges cannot be resolved by trade alone. This is also reflected in the primary source derived leverage points beyond the EUDR, most of which must be resolved or implemented especially on the

supply side. Were the EUDR to be implemented successfully, it could contribute toward achieving or triggering different of these identified leverage points. For instance, the most frequently mentioned leverage point, “ensure monitoring and enforcement for legal compliance”, could benefit from EUDR implementation, since the EUDR contains a standard requiring legal compliance with laws in the country of origin. In this way, the EUDR could support by creating demand for the legality of production and trade. Likewise, the EUDR can be expected to contribute toward exploiting the leverage point “strong traceability system, and improve information and transparency in supply chains” due to the fact that the regulation establishes strict information requirements along supply chains, which can enhance traceability and transparency of international trade.

However, it appears that most other leverage points would not directly benefit from the EUDR itself, such as “positive economic and market incentives”, “strengthen and support local capacities”, “collaboration and partnerships, and political will “, or “revise and strengthen regulatory frameworks”. Yet, measures complementary to the EUDR could help address some of these. For instance, regarding an efficient application of EUDR Article 30 on international cooperation, different initiatives have been put into place, such as the ‘Forest Partnerships’, ‘Team Europe Initiative’ and ‘The Sustainable Agriculture for Forest Ecosystems (SAFE) Project’, with the intent to support the implementation of the EUDR in producer countries.

At the same time, it would seem that many leverage points have little to no direct relevance to the EUDR or trade and would need other channels for the EU to support their implementation. For example, “clarify land tenure & policy, and address land grabbing and speculation”, “fight corruption”, or “address criminal networks in connection to deforestation” are leverage points that would need to be tackled through different agendas, if the EU wanted to explicitly support their realization. This also speaks to the point that a majority of tropical deforestation linked to agriculture is not for export demand but for domestic consumption, and hence not directly related to the EUDR as a trade-based measure.

These issues are important to keep in mind when setting expectations for the EUDR and other similar emerging trade-based demand-side measures (e.g., in the UK and the US). Even if several major demand markets adopted such instruments, it is essential to acknowledge that such measures provide limited leverage over tropical deforestation and forest degradation. Hence, it should be made explicit what they can address and what can be expected of them, and what is out of reach for them. In this vein, international cooperation remains crucial in jointly identifying the direct and indirect causes of deforestation and the ways to fight them.

7 CONCLUSION

Deforestation and forest degradation are complex issues that need to be tackled from multiple angles. Demand side transnational measures like the EUDR are arguably needed but also not enough by themselves. As we have shown in this Deliverable, the ToC of the EUDR contains several critical assumptions that would all need to “go right” in order for the EUDR to plainly achieve its intended ultimate impacts. However, this appears to be a difficult and even unlikely feat based on relevant CLEVER work packages 4 and 5 insights synthesized along the EUDR’s ToC and stakeholder interviews. We are more likely to see significant EUDR effects on ‘clean EU supply chains’, yet quite moderate impacts only on avoiding deforestation and forest degradation.

At best, a plausibly dynamic EUDR effect could be unleashed if an increase in deforestation-free EU-bound supply chains was to be accompanied by a Brussels effect of EUDR-like policy replications in other consumer regions – which could contribute to reduction of global deforestation. Absent such large-scale replications in other markets, however, we may see only negligible changes in net deforestation and forest degradation at a global level given leakage and in particular market segregation effects.

While in these optimistic and realistic scenarios, an effective fulfilment of the EUDR’s direct policy goal (‘clean supply chains’) could possibly be achieved, incomplete effectiveness as regards its global aspirations is very likely; the reality-driven scenarios may nevertheless show also other key weak points in the “telecoupled” system of production, trade and consumption of FRCs. In a worst-case scenario, the EUDR could cause further friction in trade and collaborative efforts between the EU and supply side countries, and through policy incoherence induce unintended consequences in terms of undermining effects of other policies and governance mechanisms. It can also result in marginalization and exclusion of smallholders from the EU market due to their limited capacity to adhere to the EUDR’s requirements.

Trade-based demand-side measures like the EUDR provide limited leverage over biodiversity-positive transformative change along international non-food biomass supply chains. Important leverage points, like ensuring monitoring and enforcement for legal compliance, strengthening and supporting local capacities, or clarifying land tenure and policy must be simultaneously addressed, particularly on the supply-side. These remain usually a primary responsibility of public actors and national policies. Therefore, it is essential to seek international cooperation for jointly identifying the direct and indirect causes of deforestation and the ways to fight them.

8 PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED

This Deliverable synthesized relevant work package 4 and 5 insights along the EUDR's ToC, gauging potential environmental and socio-economic effects and effectiveness of the EUDR. It further identified actor-specific leverage points for transformative change. The insights will help us understand the results of work package 3, create scenarios in work package 7, and identify solutions in the CLEVER innovation action pool in work package 8.

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